

A TWO-STEP METHOD OF GEOMORPHOLOGICAL MAPPING FOR THE CLASSIFICATION OF SLOPE MOVEMENTS AND FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO EROSION AND LANDSCAPE EVOLUTION ⁽¹⁾

UN METODO EN DOS ETAPAS PARA LA CARTOGRAFIA GEOMORFOLOGICA PARA LA CLASIFICACION DE MOVIMIENTOS DE VERTIENTE Y PARA LA EVALUACION DE SU CONTRIBUCION A LA EROSION Y A LA EVOLUCION DEL PAISAJE ⁽¹⁾

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RESUMEN

Se describe un método basado en mapas geomorfológicos a escalas 1:20.000 y 1:5.000, especialmente diseñados para el estudio de inestabilidad de pendientes. El método se concibe como un sistema tipo "zoom", mediante el cual, a escala 1:5.000, se representan, clasifican y analizan detalladamente, los movimientos en forma individual, mientras que el establecimiento de una cronología relativa y la determinación de los factores condicionantes de cada clase de movimiento se obtienen a partir del mapa 1:20.000, el cual incluye algunos rasgos seleccionados del anterior, junto con otra información geológica y geomorfológica.

La presencia de distintos tipos de rasgos microgeomorfológicos, indicativos del grado de actividad de los movimientos, se utiliza para establecer una jerarquía relativa de inestabilidad. Los mapas realizados, junto con los datos de campo sobre los espesores de los depósitos, se utilizan para cuantificar la contribución de estos procesos a la erosión en el área estudiada.

ABSTRACT

A method of geomorphological mapping at the scales 1:20,00 and 1:5,000, especially designed for slope instability assessment, is described. The method is conceived as a "zoom" system, by means of which detailed analysis, representation and classification of individual movements/areas are carried out at the 1:5,000 scale, whereas the establishment of relative chronology and determination of conditioning factors of each kind of movement are obtained through the use of 1:20,000 maps, which include selected features/data from former.

The appearance of different kinds of microgeomorphological features, indicative of activity of the movements, is used to establish a relative rank of slope instability. The maps, together with field data about thickness of the deposits, are used to quantify the contribution of these processes to erosion in the study area.

INTRODUCTION

Geomorphological mapping has been, for many years, an important tool for the understanding of landscape evolution and, in particular, for the

assessment of slope instability or susceptibility to mass movements. The use of geomorphological maps for slope instability assessment has received considerable attention in Europe during the last twenty years. A good review of methods and procedures can be found in A. Hansen (1984). Examples of specific work in different countries are contained, among others, in the publications by Brunsden et al. (1975), Gardiner & Dackombe (1983) in the U.K.; Champetier de Ribes (1987), Humbert (1977) in France; Canuti et al. (1979), Carrara & Merenda (1974, 1976), Rodolfi et al.

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(1979), Panizza (1990) in Italy; Mahr & Bailak (1973), Mahr & Malgot (1978) in Czechoslovakia; Seijmonsbergen et al. (1988), Simons (1986) in Holland; Irigaray & Chacón (1990), Corominas (1992) in Spain. Often, these maps are rather complex documents, difficult to read and to interpret in terms of present hazards and in relation to the contribution of landsliding and other mass movements to the evolution of landscape.

In this paper we propose a method of mapping at two different scales and levels of detail, 1:5.000 and 1:20.000, aimed at combining, on the one hand, information relevant for hazard assessment and, on the other hand, information relative to historical-Holocene landscape evolution.

The application of this method is demonstrated in the Cantabrian Range, northern Spain (Figure 1), in an area with altitudes between 200 and 800 m, slope gradients around 30% and temperate,

humid climate (about 13°C average temperature and 1500 mm yearly rainfall). The area is formed by moderately and fractured Mesozoic rocks. Many of the fractures in the area are related to the diapiric activity of Triassic clays and evaporites, which continued into the Quaternary, well after Alpine tectonic activity ended.

METODOLOGY

Landslide mapping ("sensu lato") is normally based on the identification and representation of a series of factors or parameters which have influence in this process, as well as some interpretative features such as type of movement, triggering cause, etc., the "discriminating factors" (M.J. Hansen, 1984) listed in Table 1, for which information can be gathered by air photo interpretation or by field survey. The difficulty, as stated above, arises when all relevant factors have to be represented in one map meant to serve several purposes.

TABLE 1

Discriminating factors in landslide mapping and methods of survey
(Modified after M.J. Hansen, 1984)

			Survey ■ : air photo □ field
1.	Relative age of movement	■	Zaruba & Mencil (1969)
2.	Degree of activity	■ □	Erskine (1973); Zaruba & Mencil (1969)
3.	Geographic type	□	Reynolds (1932)
4.	Geographic location	■	Reynolds (1932)
5.	Orientation	■	Cendrero et al. (1987)
6.	Climatic type	□	Sharpe (1938); Hutchinson & Bhandori (1971)
7.	Type and size of material involved	■ □	Coates (1977); Varnes (1978); Zaruba & Mencil (1969)
8.	Surficial and bedrock geology	■ □	Ladd (1935); Zaruba & Mencil (1969)
9.	Type of movement	■ □	Coates (1977); Hutchinson (1968); Sharpe (1938); Varnes (1978); Ward (1945); Flageollet (1988)
10.	Relative velocity of movement	■ □	Varnes (1958, 1978)
11.	Percentage of voids	□	Sharpe (1938); Brunsden (1979)
12.	Transporting agent	□	Terzaghi (1950); Varnes (1978); Brunsden (1979)
13.	Triggering mechanisms	□	Terzaghi (1950); Brunsden (1979)
14.	Morphology the material deposited	■	Blong (1973 a, b); Crozier (1973); Rapp (1960)
15.	Morphology of the failure	■ □	Blong (1973 a, b); Skempton (1953); Davidson (1965)
16.	Transporting agent	□	Flageollet (1988)
17.	Presence and type of discontinuities	■ □	Millies-Lacroix (1981); Szabo (1985)

The methodology described here includes a first stage of air photo survey, using a check card based on the one proposed by Carrara & Merenda (1976), by means of which information regarding 43 items is gathered for each individual mass movement identified. These movements are mapped at the 1:5.000 scale, using the legend shown in **Figure 2**. The map thus obtained is then checked by the usual tuyepe of field survey.

The second stage consists in the air photo interpretation of geological, structural and geomorphological features, other than the ones directly referring to mass movements, and their representation at the 1:20.000 scale, trying to establish a relative chronology for the different slope instability events and other geomorphological processes, (see **Figure 3**). Thus, the initial, 1:5.000 scale map can be considered as a "thematic landslide map" in which microgeomorphological features are represented, as well as the type of movement (Varnes, 1978) and other discriminating factors. This map provides the basis for initial slope instability assessment. Six potential instability classes were defined using the following criteria (see **Figure 2**):

1. Areas without any visible sign of instability.
2. Areas without signs of landslides or flows but with visible signs of creep.
3. Areas with signs of creep, very eroded landslide scars, landslide and flow deposits without surficial fissures.
3. Areas with slightly eroded landslide and/or flow deposits and scars, without surficial fissures.
4. Very well preserved landslide or rock fall scars, with sharp landforms, numerous surficial fissures parallel to the main scarp.
5. Numerous surficial landslides and flows practically un-eroded, and numerous active surficial fissures.

The 1/20.000 scale map, on the other hand, has the meaning of an "integrated map" in which bedrock and structure are represented together with geomorphological features, both related to slope movements and to other process (see **Figure 3**). In this map a tentative relative chronology of the movements has been indicated as well. This chronology was established by observa-

tion of the relationships between the different movements and between these and fluvial landforms and deposits.

The oldest generation of slope movements has been initially considered to be Pleistocene, because they are older than the 2-4 m fluvial terrace, which in this region corresponds to the Holocene (IGME, 1979). These are large deposits which have been eroded by the widening of the fluvial valley. The second generation is formed by smaller deep landslides, which affect the 2-4 m terrace. The third generation includes a few small deep landslides, surficial landslides and flows; in some cases these movements have affected the alluvial floodplain. Finally, the fourth generation is represented by scattered surficial landslides and flows, normally related to recent undercutting of slopes by fluvial erosion. Although there are no absolute age determinations, the different "generations" of slope movements have been tentatively assigned to: Pleistocene, "Holocene", (10.000-1.000 B.P.?), "historical" (10.000-1.000 B.P.?) and "recent" (less than 100 B.P.?).

RESULTS

Even though the area represented in **Figure 2** is small and not exactly representative of the whole study zone, it can be seen that classes 4 and 5 of slope instability, the ones which, in principle, represent a clear hazard from the human point of review, amount to 14,4% of the area surveyed.

The spatial relationships between the different types of movements and lithological, structural and geomorphological features depicted in **Figure 3** provide some clues with respect to the factors conditioning the occurrence of slope instability. An analysis of the distribution of Holocene movements among the different lithologies in the area (see **Table 2**), shows that the most unstable type of bedrock is, by far, the Keuper facies (Triassic clays and evaporites), with 50% of its area affected by instability. The weathered ophites, with a well-developed saprolite, come after, with 19.2% of their surface affected. The alternating beds or Jurassic marls and limestones show instability in 11.5% of their outcrops, and in sandstones and siltstones of the Buntsandstein facies only 7% has been affected.

FIGURE 2

Landslide map, 1:5,000. A: Type of movement; A1: Rockfall; A2: landslide; A3: Flow. B: Relative velocity; B1: Slow; B2: Moderate; B3: Rapid. C: Type of material involved; C1: Regolith; C2: Soft bedrock; C3: Hard bedrock. D: Present degree of activity; D1: No signs of activity; D2: Some signs of activity; D3: Clear signs of activity. E: Geomorphological features of landslides; 1: Information regarding A, B, C and D. 2: Crown; 3: Tongue; 4: Micromorphological features. 2a: External limit of movement; 2b: Main scarp; 2c: Partly eroded crown; 2d: Fissures denoting future failure. 3a: Head of tongue and direction of movement. 4a: Oblique fissures; 4b: Radial fissures; 4c: Scarp; 4d: Accumulation lobes; 4e: Ponds and moist flats. F: Debris cones. G: Talweg. H: Slope instability class; H0: Minimum instability; H5: Maximum instability.

FIGURE 3

Geological and geomorphological map, 1:20.000. 1: Buntsandstein, sandstones and silts-tones; 2: Keuper, clays and evaporites; 3: Ophites; 4: Jurassic limestones, dolostones and marls; 5: Rockfalls; 6: Landslides; 7: Flows; 8: Debris cones; 9: Older torrential cones; 10: Younger torrential cones; 11: Upper terraces; 12: Lower terraces; 13: Floodplain; 14: Remains of Pleistocene landslide and/or flow deposits; 15: Talweg; 16: Terracettes; 17: Convex slope break on valley slopes; 18: Dolines; 19: Scarp; 20: Fault; 21: Contact; A, B, C: First, second and third; generations of Holocene movements. F: Flows; S: Slides; R: Rockfalls. 22: Rills.

TABLE 2
Distribution of movements among different lithologies.
1: Rockfalls, 2: Flows, 4: Landslides

	Bedrock	Type Movem.	No.	Surface (ha)	% Bedrock surface	% Surface study area	Side %	
							Sunny	Shady
	BUTSANDSTEIN	1						
	272.4	2	5	14.16	5.19	1.6	5	95
	ha	3	12	4.86	1.78	0.5		100
TOTAL			17	16.82	7.0			
	OPHITES	1						
	127	2	14	16.1	12.6	1.8	50	50
	ha	3	8	8.4	6.61	0.9	37	63
TOTAL			22	24.5	19.2			
	KEUPER	1						
	130.8	2	42	39.8	30	4.5	5	95
	ha	3	6	26.3	20	3.0	16	84
TOTAL			48	66.1	50			
	JURASSIC	1	1	1.8	0.5	0.2		
	342.8	2	18	25.87	7.5	2.9	100	
	ha	3	2	39.83	3.5	1.3	100	
TOTAL			21	21	11.5		50	50
TOTAL			108	103.25				

Not only the frequency, but also the type of movement varies according to lithology (Table 2), with flows as the predominant process on the Keuper facies; also, but, to a lesser extent, on Jurassic marls and limestones and ophites. Landslides appear as the main type of movement on the Buntsandstein facies.

Structural discontinuities are another important conditioning factor. Figure 3 shows that a large proportion of landslides occurring on the Jurassic, the Buntsandstein facies, or the Keuper facies, near its contact with the Jurassic, have their crown controlled by fractures. Most of these are deep landslides of the older Holocene "genera-

tion" (in the case of Pleistocene movements, the relationship cannot be defined clearly, because the crowns are eroded and difficult to locate with precision). Orientation of the slopes also appears to have an influence on the process, as, for a given lithology, movements tend to be more frequent on the shady sides, where ground moisture is higher. Nevertheless, this point requires more detailed analysis.

The data presented above provide the basis for a preliminary assessment of the contribution of mass movements to landscape evolution in this area. First of all, it seems that landforms and deposits produced by mass movements are removed by erosion, in general, in periods not much greater than 10,000 years, as only a few remains of very large Pleistocene landslides can presently be recognised. Deep landslides affecting bedrock, with dimensions in order of 10,000 to 40,000 m² seem to remain as visible features of the landscape for a few thousands of years, as indicated by the relatively good preservation of the deposits and landforms corresponding to the older "generation" of Holocene movements. Surficial landslides and flows affecting mostly the regolith and with dimensions not greater than 60,000 m² have a much shorter "landscape life", probably no longer than a few centuries, as this kind of movements can only be observed among the third and, to a lesser extent, second Holocene "generations".

Landslides and other slope movements appear to be an important mechanism of mass transfer in this region. A preliminary estimate of the volumes involved in the area represented in **Figure 2**, where some data about thickness of the different types of deposits are available (approximately 30 m average for landslides, 5 m for flows and 3 m for rockfalls), indicates that Holocene landslides have removed about 8.3 Hm³, flows 1.6 Hm³ and rockfalls 0.05 Hm³. If this estimate is extended to the area in **Figure 3**, taking into account the relative surfaces occupied by different types of deposits, the volumes obtained are: 40.53, 5.2 and 0.54 Hm³ respectively. As the total area surveyed is 8.75 km², this amounts to 52,880 m³/Ha; that is, a volume equivalent to a uniform thickness of 500 cm, or to a uniform erosion of about 0.5 mm/year. These figures are only a rough preliminary estimate and should not be taken as established

values; they are simply meant to provide an idea of the order of magnitude of these processes in the region.

CONCLUSIONS

The methodology described makes the detailed, objective representation of terrain features directly related to slope instability, easy and straightforward. Interpretative characteristics of the different movements can also be depicted clearly. The formulation of certain criteria, based on the classification of observable terrain features, makes it possible to establish a clearly defined rank of slope instability classes. These, in turn, provide the basis for slope instability hazard assessment.

The 1:20,000 scale representation of the distribution, type and relative age of different mass movements, together with other geomorphological and geological features, enables the identification of possible conditioning factors for the process. These appear to be, mainly, bedrock type and existing fractures.

A relative chronology for the movements (and a first approximation to a more precise chronology) can also be established, on the basis of the relationships between slope deposits and other geomorphological characteristics, particularly fluvial deposits and landforms. The availability of one or two absolute age data in any point of the relative time scale obtained, would make the tentative chronology proposed much more precise.

It can tentatively be concluded that landforms and deposits produced by mass movements in this region have, on the whole, a "life time" not longer than 10,000 years in the case of deep landslides, and less than 1,000 years for surficial landslides. In a first approximation, the volumes involved in Holocene mass wasting are estimated to be about 12 Tm Ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, equivalent to a uniform "erosion" of 0.5 mm year⁻¹. This is an order of magnitude greater than the rates of present hydric erosion reported in other parts of northern Spain (Benito et al., 1991).

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